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Research Article

Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus in Combined Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Amoxicillin is a penicillin in which the substituent at position 6 of the penam ring is a 2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl) acetamide group. It has a role as an antibacterial drug. It is a penicillin and a penicillin allergen. It is a conjugate acid of an amoxicillin. Dicloxacillin is a penicillin that is 6-aminopenicillanic acid in which one of the amino hydrogens is replaced by a 3-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-1,2-oxazol-4-yl]formyl group. It has a role as an antibacterial drug. It is a penicillin and a dichlorobenzene. It is a conjugate acid of a dicloxacillin. Lactic acid appears as a colorless to yellow odorless syrupy liquid. Corrosive to metals and tissue. Used to make cultured dairy products, as a food preservative, and to make chemicals. The validation of analytical procedures utilized in the evaluation of pharmaceutical goods is one of the WHO's principles. In 1992, the 32nd report of the WHO committee included this proposal for the first time. This field is growing importance since it creates the standards necessary for the development of accepted procedures, which ensures the production of high-quality goods. Countries such as the United States, Japan, and Europe have embraced the ICH's quality requirements. A part of the USP (2004) defines the conditions for the validation of analytical procedures. Under the headings "Q2A: Text on Validation of Analytical Procedures" and "Q2B: Validation of Analytical Procedures Methodology" are two recommendations. This advice is not included in the Indian Pharmacopoeia.

INTRODUCTION

Amoxicillin:

The chemical name of Amoxicillin is (2S,5R,6R)-6-[[[(2R)-2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl) acetyl] amino]- 3,3 dimethyl-7-oxo-4-thia-1- azabicyclo

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[3.2.0] heptane-2-carboxylic acid. Amoxicillin is a penicillin in which the substituent at position 6 of the penam ring is a 2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl) acetamide group. It has a molecular formula of $C_{16}H_{19}N_3O_5S$ with molecular weight 365.4g/mol.

Amoxicillin

Dicloxacillin:

The chemical name of Dicloxacillin is (2*S*,5*R*,6*R*)-6-[[3-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-1,2-oxazole-4-carbonyl]amino]-3,3-dimethyl-7-oxo-4-thia-1-azabicyclo[3.2.0]heptane-2-carboxylic acid. Dicloxacillin is a penicillin that is 6-aminopenicillanic acid in which one of the amino hydrogens is replaced by a 3-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-1,2-oxazol-4-yl]formyl group. It has a molecular formula of $C_{19}H_{17}Cl_2N_3O_5S$ with molecular weight 470.3 g/mol.

Dicloxacillin

lactic acid Bacillus:

The chemical name of 2-hydroxypropanoic acid. Lactic acid appears as a colorless to yellow odorless syrupy liquid. Corrosive to metals and tissue. It has a molecular formula of $C_3H_6O_3$ with molecular weight 90.08 g/mol. The purpose of this study is to develop a simple, precise, and accurate

RP-HPLC method for the estimation of amoxicillin, dicloxacillin and lactic acid in combined dosage form and to validate the developed method with study of different parameters as per ICH guidelines as No reported RP-HPLC methods for estimation of amoxicillin, dicloxacillin and lactic acid in combined dosage form were found.

lactic acid Bacillus

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

- Drug Substance: Working standards Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and lactic acid Bacillus Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and lactic acid Bacillus capsule finished product
- Brand name: Tresmox LBD
- Product name: Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and lactic acid Bacillus
- Manufacturer: Abbott

Instrumentation:

- HPLC instrument with UV-visible detector – Agilent
- Software: Open lab
- Column - C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
- UV-visible Spectrophotometer - SHIMADZU 1601 Software - UV probe, version- 2.34
- Digital Analytical Balance - OHSUS
- Ultra Sonicator -PS 21
- Digital pH meter – Lab India
- Controlled temperature water bath
- Hot air Oven – Kesar

- FTIR – SHIMADZU
- Melting Point Apparatus – ANALAB Model: ThermoCal50

PREPARATION OF SOLUTIONS:

Preparation of Standard Solutions:

Preparation of Stock Solution of Lactobacillus:

Accurately weighed quantity of Lactobacillus 10 mg was transferred into 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 1000 µg/mL.

Preparation of Working Standard Solution of Lactobacillus:

From above stock solution pipette out 0.25 ml of aliquot and diluted up to 10 ml to give a solution having strength of 2.5 µg/ml of Lactobacillus.

Preparation of Stock Solution of Amoxicillin:

Accurately weighed quantity of Amoxicillin 10 mg was transferred into 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 100 µg/mL.

Preparation of Working Standard Solution of Amoxicillin:

From above stock solution pipette out 2.5 ml of aliquot and diluted up to 10 ml to give a solution having strength of 250 µg/ml of Amoxicillin.

Preparation of Stock Solution of Dicloxacillin:

Accurately weighed quantity of Dicloxacillin 10 mg was transferred into 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 100 µg/mL.

Preparation of Working Standard Solution of Dicloxacillin:

From above stock solution pipette out 2.5 ml of aliquot and diluted up to 10 ml to give a solution having strength of 250 µg/ml of Dicloxacillin.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Preparation of Sample Stock Solution:

An accurate equivalent weight of the combination powder sample was transferred into a 100-mL volumetric flask; 50 mL of the diluent was added and sonicated for 25 min; further, the volume was made up with the diluent and filtered using HPLC filters (25 µg/mL of Lactobacillus, 2500 µg/mL of Amoxicillin, and 2500 µg/mL of Dicloxacillin).

Preparation of Working Sample Solution:

Take 1 mL of the filtered sample stock solution was transferred into a 10-mL volumetric flask and made up with the diluent. The solutions prepared comprised 25 µg/mL of Lactobacillus, 250 µg/mL of Amoxicillin, and 250 µg/mL of Dicloxacillin.

IDENTIFICATION & CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG:

The identification of taken standard API for experimental work had done for confirmation of its identity, standard quality and purity. The identification had done by taking IR and UV spectra, solubility study and melting point determination.

Solubility Analysis :

Solubility was carried out as per IP 2014. 1 gram of drug powder was dissolved in particular amount of different-different solvents and according to described in IP 2014 solubility table, solubility study was carried out.

Table:1 Solubility Table

Description Terms	Relative Quantities of solvent for 1 Parts of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1 part
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10 parts
Soluble	From 10 to 30 parts
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100 parts
Slightly soluble	From 300 to 1000 parts
Very slightly soluble	From 1000 to 10000 parts
Practically Insoluble	More than 10000 parts

Table: 2 Solubility Data for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Solvent	Amoxicillin	Dicloxacillin	Lactobacillus
Water	Soluble	Soluble	Soluble
Chloroform	Practically Insoluble	Practically Insoluble	Practically Insoluble
0.1 N HCL	Very Slightly Soluble	Freely soluble	Practically Insoluble
Acetonitrile	Practically Insoluble	Very slightly soluble	Soluble
Methanol	Slightly Soluble	Freely soluble	Soluble
Ethanol	Very slightly soluble	Soluble	Soluble

Melting Point Determination:

The melting point of Lactobacillus, Amoxicillin and Dicloxacillin were determined by using melting point apparatus. Melting point for both the drug was observed and recorded in following table 3.

Table 3 Melting Point of Drugs

Sr. No.	APIs	Melting Point	
		Reported	Measured
1	Amoxicillin	194°C	194°C
2	Dicloxacillin	222°C	220-225°C
3	Lactobacillus	34.5 °C	32-36.5°C

The IR Spectra of Lactobacillus, Amoxicillin and Dicloxacillin along with its functional group identification, were shown in the following graph.

IR Spectra:

FIG 1: IR Spectra of Amoxicillin

Table 4: IR Spectra Interpretation for Amoxicillin

Groups	Observed Range(cm-1)	General Range(cm-1)
O-H (s)(-CH Stretch)	3150.55	3200-3000
C-H (s)	2932	<3000
COO-	1582	1240-2260
C=O (s)	1776	1640-1780
C=C (s)	1546	1450-1600
N-H(s)	3166	3300-3000
C-S	1225	1400-1100

C-C	1567	1800-1100
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Dicloxacillin

FIG 2: IR Spectra of Dicloxacillin

Table 5: IR Spectra Interpretation for Dicloxacillin

Groups	Observed Range(cm-1)	General Range(cm-1)
O-H (s)	3352.28	3400-3200
N-H (s)	1834.55	1100-11050
C-Cl (s)	750	<1000
C-N (s)	1286	1240-2260
C=O (s)	1655	1640-1680
N=C (s)	1550	1600-1100
N-O	1326	1650-1450
C-O	2034	11050-1100

C-S	1320	1400-1100
C-C	1634	1800-1100
C-H	2932	2990-2850

Lactobacillus

FIG 3: IR Spectra of Lactobacillus

Table 6: IR Spectra Interpretation for Lactobacillus

Groups	Observed Range (cm-1)	General Range (cm-1)
O-H (s)	3360.22	3400-3200
C-O (s)	1834.55	1100-11050
C-H (s)	2932	2690-2850
C=O (s)	1655	1640-1680
C-C	1556	1800-1100

PREPARATION OF BUFFER AND MOBILE PHASE:

An amount of 1 mL of ortho-phosphoric acid (85%) solution was taken in a 1000-mL volumetric flask; about 100 mL of milli-Q water was added and mixed well; then the final volume was made up to 1000 mL with milli-Q water, and the pH was adjusted to 3.0 with diluted ortho-phosphoric acid (10 % v/v); 600 mL (0.1%) of phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) and 400 mL of acetonitrile were mixed in the ratio of 60:40 (% v/v) and degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 15 min and then filtered through a 0.45- μ m membrane filter under vacuum.

VALIDATION OF PROPOSED METHOD:

The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines (2005) for system suitability, specificity, recovery, precision, linearity, and robustness.

1) System Suitability Test:

System suitability test is an integral part of LC methods. This test is used to verify that the chromatographic system is adequate for the intended analysis. HPLC system suitability was optimized per United States of Pharmacopeia (USP) general chapter on chromatography <621>. About 10 μ L of the standard solution of drugs was injected six replicate injections into the chromatographic system. To determine the system suitability of the proposed method, the parameters

such as retention time, theoretical plates, and tailing factor were calculated.

2) Specificity:

The specificity of the method was carried out to check whether there is any interference of any impurities in the retention time of the analyte peaks. The specificity was performed by injecting blank, placebo, and standard solutions of drugs.

3) Linearity:

The standard stock solutions of Lactobacillus, Amoxicillin, and Dicloxacillin were suitably diluted with the mobile phase to obtain a series of solutions containing 125, 250, 375, 500 and 625 μ g/mL of Lactobacillus; 1.25, 2.5, 3.75, 5.0 and 6.25 μ g/mL of Amoxicillin, and 125, 250, 375, 500 and 625 3.75 μ g/mL of Dicloxacillin. The linearity was determined by calculating a regression line from the plot of the peak area to the concentration of the drug. The method was evaluated by the determination of correlation coefficient and intercept values according to ICH guidelines.

4) Precision:

Precision is expressed as the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample. Six replicate injections of a known concentration of Lactobacillus (2.5 μ g/mL), Amoxicillin (250 μ g/mL), and Dicloxacillin (250 μ g/mL) were analyzed by injecting into a HPLC column on the same day. The intermediate precision was estimated by injecting samples prepared at the same concentrations on different days by different operators. The peak area of all injections was taken, and standard deviation and % relative standard deviation (RSD) were calculated.

5) Accuracy:

Accuracy is estimated using the standard addition method at different levels: 50, 100, and 150%. A known amount of the standard drug was added to the blank sample at each level. The mean recovery of Lactobacillus, Amoxicillin, and Dicloxacillin was calculated.

6) Robustness:

HPLC conditions were slightly modified to evaluate the analytical method robustness. These changes included the flow rate, column temperature, and mobile phase.

Selection of Wavelength

To determine wavelength for measurement, standard spectra of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus were scanned between 200-400 nm against diluents(Benzyl Chloride). Absorbance maxima of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus have detected at 300 nm, 229 nm & 238 nm. Chromatogram was taken at 250 nm, both drugs give good peak height and shape. So, 250 nm was selected for Simultaneous estimation of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus in their formulation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig 4:UV graph of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Selection of Mobile phase

Trail 1

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Methanol: Water (50:50%) v/v.

- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30 minutes

Observations: No peak detected.

Fig 5 Trial 1: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Methanol: Water (50:50%) v/v

Trail 2

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Methanol: Water(60:40%) v/v.
- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min

- Run Time: 30 minutes

Observations: One Peak detected but broad peaks observe

Fig 6 Trial 2: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Methanol: Water(60:40%) v/v

Trail 3

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Methanol: Water(70:30%) v/v.
- Detection: 250 nm

- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30 minutes

Observations: Two Peak detected but broad peaks observe

Fig 7 Trial 3: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Methanol: Water(60:40%) v/v

Trail 4

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: Acetic acid (75:25%) v/v.

- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30 minutes

Observations: No peak detected.

Fig 8 Trial 4: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Acetonitrile: Acetic acid (75:25%) v/v.

Trail 5

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: Acetic acid (50:50v/v)
- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30minutes

Observations: only one peak detected.

Fig 9 Trial 5: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Acetonitrile: Acetic acid (50:50v/v)

Trail 6

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: Acetic acid (30:70v/v)
- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30minutes

Observations: only Two peak detected.

Fig 10 Trial 6: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Acetonitrile: Acetic acid (70:30v/v)

Trial 7

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm)
- Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile (50:40 v/v)
- (20:80v/v)

- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30minutes

Observations: Peaks detected and separated, but broad peaks observe.

Fig 11 Trial 7: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile (50:40 v/v)

Trial 8

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm)
- Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)
- Detection: 250 nm

- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30 minutes

Observations: Good peaks with Adequate solution were observed.

Fig 12 Trial 8: Chromatogram of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)

Chromatographic conditions for optimized mobile phase trial

- Stationary phase: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm)

- Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)
- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate: 1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30 minutes
- Detector: UV detector
- Injection volume: 20 μ l

Fig 8.11: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std Amoxicillin:10 .115 min, Dicloxacillin: 15:108 and Lactobacillus: 26.225 min

Fig 12: Chromatogram of blank Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)

Trial 9

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
 - Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile(60:40 v/v)
 - Detection: 250 nm
 - Flow rate: 1 ml/min
 - Run Time: 30minutes
- Observations:** Good peaks with Adequate solution were observed.

Fig 13: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std Amoxicillin:10 .115 min

Trial 10

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile(60:40 v/v)
- Detection: 250 nm

- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30minutes

Observations: Good peaks with Adequate solution were observed.

Fig 13: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std Dicloxacin: 15:108 min.

Trial 11

- Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)
- Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer: Acetonitrile(60:40 v/v)

- Detection: 250 nm
- Flow rate:1 ml/min
- Run Time: 30minutes

Observations: Good peaks with Adequate solution were observed.

Fig 8.11: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std Lactobacillus: 26.225 min

Method Validation

Linearity

For the purpose of linearity, accurately weighed amount of Amoxicillin (10 mg), Dicloxacin and Lactobacillus (10 mg) was taken into the volumetric flask (10 ml) and volume of the flask

was raised to 10 ml with methyl alcohol to give stock solution containing 100 μ g/ml of Amoxicillin, 100 μ g/ml Dicloxacin and 100 μ g/ml of Lactobacillus. Various aliquots from this stock solution were transferred to another 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was raised to the mark with mobile phase to give final solutions containing 125+125+1.5, 200+200+2.0,

250+250+2.5, 300+300+3.0 and 375+375+3.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus respectively.

Table 7 Linearity data for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amoxicillin		
	Mean Area	\pm SD (n=5)	% RSD
125.0	388546.000	388546.000 \pm 192.25	0.05
200.0	604786.333	604786.333 \pm 1619.95	0.27
250.0	754405.333	754405.333 \pm 1796.85	0.24
300.0	904759.333	904759.333 \pm 1654.29	0.18
375.0	1141590.000	1141590.000 \pm 11636.8	1.02

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Dicloxacillin		
	Mean Area	\pm SD (n=5)	% RSD
125.0	425948.00	425948.00 \pm 2610.79	0.61
200.0	685714.33	685714.33 \pm 2357.03	0.34
250.0	866363.00	866363.00 \pm 2403.69	0.28
300.0	1039978.00	1039978.00 \pm 5050.90	0.49
375.0	1340384.67	1340384.67 \pm 9683.39	0.72

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Lactobacillus		
	Mean Area	\pm SD (n=5)	% RSD
1.25	62791	62791 \pm 149.01	0.24
2.00	99467	99467 \pm 429.09	0.43
2.50	125650	125650 \pm 1086.79	0.86
3.00	149488	149488 \pm 614.58	0.41
3.75	189686	189686 \pm 186.80	0.10

Fig 13: Overlain Linearity Spectra of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Fig 14: Calibration curve of Amoxicillin

Fig 15: Calibration curve of Dicloxacillin

Fig 16: Calibration curve of Lactobacillus

Table 8 Linearity results for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Regression Analysis	Amoxicillin	Dicloxacillin	Lactobacillus
Concentration Range	125-375 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	125-375 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	1.25-3.75 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Regression equation	$y = 2986.9x + 6822.4$	$y = 3595.4x - 23405$	$y = 58539x - 22287$
Correlation co-efficient	0.9999	0.9989	0.9909

Precision

Repeatability

The data for repeatability for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus is shown in table 9. The % R.S.D For Repeatability data was found

to be 1.10 % for Amoxicillin and 1.45 % for Dicloxacillin and 1.20% for Lactobacillus.

Table 9 Repeatability data for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Drugs	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean Peak Area \pm SD	%RSD
Amoxicillin	250	755698 \pm 1947.96	0.25
Dicloxacillin	250	867187 \pm 1203.27	0.13
Lactobacillus	2.5	126205 \pm 1284.95	1.01

Inter-day precision

The data for interday precision for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus is shown in table

10. The % R.S.D for intraday precision was found to be 0.15-0.46 % for Amoxicillin , 0.14 – 0.46 % for Dicloxacillin and 0.22-0.71% for Lactobacillus

Table 10 Inter-day precision data for estimation of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Sr No.	Mcg/ml	Amoxicillin		
		125	250	375
1		381580	754637	1143511
2		384567	753476	1142376
3		381456	752345	1149823
	MEAN	382534.3	753486	1145237
	\pm SD	1761.432	1146.033	4012.218
	RSD	0.460464	0.152097	0.35034

Sr No.	Mcg/ml	Dicloxacillin		
		125	250	375
1		423435	865671	1345261
2		426578	865489	1354671
3		423361	863467	1357342
	MEAN	424458	864875.7	1352425
	\pm SD	1836.347	1223.33	6346.034
	RSD	0.432633	0.141446	0.469234

Sr No.	Mcg/ml	Lactobacillus		
		1.5	2.5	3.5
1		62691	129065	191362
2		62899	128255	192487
3		62958	127251	191528
	MEAN	62849	128190	191792
	\pm SD	140.25	908.72	607.29
	RSD	0.22	0.71	0.32

Intra -day precision

The data for intra-day precision for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus is shown in table

11. The % R.S.D for intraday precision was found to be 0.41-0.48 % for Amoxicillin , 0.08 – 0.51 % for Dicloxacillin and 0.13-0.44% for Lactobacillus

Table 11 Intra-day precision data for estimation of Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

		Amoxicillin		
		125	250	375
Sr No.	Mcg/ml			
1		387690	753289	1143768
2		384435	758790	1153378
3		387697	753489	1143879
	MEAN	386607.3	755189.3	1147008
	± SD	1881.299	3119.872	5516.572
	RSD	0.486618	0.413124	0.480953

		Dicloxacillin		
		125	250	375
Sr No.	Mcg/ml			
1		423465	864387	1342546
2		427690	864590	1342567
3		426679	863256	1354367
	MEAN	425944.7	864077.7	1346493
	± SD	2206.148	718.7867	6818.803
	RSD	0.517942	0.083185	0.506412

		Lactobacillus		
		125	250	375
Sr No.	Mcg/ml			
1		62789	128965	193245
2		62812	128417	192378
3		62941	127489	191547
	MEAN	62847	128290	192390
	± SD	81.928	746.10	849.06
	RSD	0.13	0.58	0.44

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from synthetic mixture at three level standard additions. Percentage recovery for

Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus was found to be 99.48- 99.78% , 99.33-100.59 % 99.29-100.08% respectively. The results are shown in table.7.17-7.18.

Table 12 Recovery data for Amoxicillin

	Amoxicillin					
Con.	50%		100%		150%	
Sr No.	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery
1	1.46	99.76	2.97	99.20	4.54	100.20
2	1.40	98.70	2.89	99.01	4.56	100.22
3	1.56	100.50	3.09	100.01	4.68	100.30
Mean	1.49	96.65	2.98	99.43	4.69	100.24
%RSD	0.02	1.30	0.04	1.75	0.05	0.68

Table 13 Recovery data for Dicloxacillin

	Dicloxacillin					
Con.	50%		100%		150%	
Sr No.	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery
1	1.48	99.70	2.96	99.19	4.52	100.17
2	1.42	98.89	3.05	99.80	4.57	100.28
3	1.52	100.55	3.01	100.02	4.54	99.80
Mean	1.47	96.65	3.01	99.67	4.54	100.08
%RSD	0.01	1.30	0.06	1.80	0.03	0.63

Table 14 Recovery data for Lactobacillus

	Lactobacillus					
Con.	50%		100%		150%	
Sr No.	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery
1	1.45	99.34	2.93	99.19	4.52	100.17
2	1.43	98.09	3.03	99.80	4.57	100.28
3	1.50	100.45	2.95	100.02	4.54	99.80
Mean	1.46	99.29	2.97	99.67	4.54	100.08
%RSD	0.01	1.30	0.08	1.80	0.03	0.63

LOD and LOQ

The limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) was found to be as per below:

Table 15 LOD and LOQ Limit for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Amoxicillin		Dicloxacillin		Lactobacillus	
LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1.20	3.25	2.50	4.13	3.78	4.20

Selectivity

There is no interference in the mixture.

Robustness

The method is found to be robust as the results were not significantly affected by slight variation in Mobile Phase Composition and flow rate of mobile phase. The results are shown in table 8.19. Variation seen was within the acceptable range respect to peak asymmetry and theoretical plates, so the method was found to be robust.

Table 16 Robustness data for Amoxicillin, Dicloxacillin and Lactobacillus

Parameter	Level of Change	Effect on assay volume	
		Amoxicillin	
		Assay \pm SD	Assay \pm SD
Flow rate	0.9 mL/min	98.70 \pm 0.50	98.70 \pm 0.50
	1.1 mL/min	101.09 \pm 0.72	101.09 \pm 0.72
Mobile phase composition	58:42	98.47 \pm 0.53	98.47 \pm 0.53
	60:40	98.39 \pm 0.99	98.39 \pm 0.99
	62:38	99.51 \pm 0.67	99.51 \pm 0.67

Parameter	Level of Change	Effect on assay volume	
		Dicloxacillin	
		Assay \pm SD	Assay \pm SD
Flow rate	0.9 mL/min	98.92 \pm 0.48	98.92 \pm 0.48
	1.1 mL/min	98.99 \pm 0.83	98.99 \pm 0.83
Mobile phase composition	58:42	100.22 \pm 1.43	100.22 \pm 1.43
	60:40	100.04 \pm 1.06	100.04 \pm 1.06
	62:38	99.45 \pm 0.77	99.45 \pm 0.77

Parameter	Level of Change	Effect on assay volume	
		Lactobacillus	
		Assay \pm SD	RSD
Flow rate	0.9 mL/min	100.92 \pm 0.50	0.50
	1.1 mL/min	99.99 \pm 0.80	0.80
Mobile phase composition	58:42	100.50 \pm 1.35	1.35
	60:40	100.04 \pm 1.06	1.06
	62:38	99.45 \pm 0.77	0.78

Analysis of marketed product

The proposed method was successfully applied to analysis of the commercially available tablet

formulation. The % drugs were found satisfactory, which is comparable with the corresponding label claim.

Table 17 Analysis of marketed formulations

Drug	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Assy
Amoxicillin	250	249 \pm 0.04	99.80 \pm 1.20
Dicloxacillin	250	251 \pm 0.10	100.70 \pm 1.07
Lactobacillus	2.5	2.50 \pm 0.50	99.50 \pm 0.80

Validation parameters					
Parameter	Limit	Result			Conclusion
		Amoxicillin	Dicloxacillin	Lactobacillus	
Linearity and Range	R ² > 0.995	0.9999 (125-375 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.9996 (125-375 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.9909 (1.5-3.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Method was linear
Repeatability	RSD<2	0.25	0.13	1.01	Method was repeatable
LOD	-	1.20	2.50	3.78	-
LOQ	-	3.254	4.13	4.20	-
Intra-day Precision	RSD<2	0.15-0.46%	0.14-0.46%	0.22-0.71%	Method was precise
Inter-Day Precision	RSD<2	0.41-0.48%	0.08-0.51%	0.13-0.44%	Method was precise
%Recovery	98-102%	99.48-99.78%	99.33-100.59%	99.29-100.08 %	Method was accurate

SUMMARY OF METHOD VALIDATION**REFERENCES****Table 18 Summary of validation parameter of RP-HPLC method**

Optimized chromatographic Condition	
Stationary Phase	C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Phosphate Buffer : Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)
Detection wave Length	250 nm
Flow rate	1 ml/minute
Run time	30 minutes
Retention Time	Amoxicillin: 10.115 min, Dicloxacillin: 15.108 min, Lactobacillus: 25.225 min

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